

STRAIN MEASUREMENT OF 3D PRINTED SHORT CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS USING ELECTRIC PROPERTY

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ABSTRACT

3D printed short carbon fiber reinforced plastic (SCFRP) can be easily manufactured in complicated shapes. SCFRP is expected to be applicable for fastening members and structures. Structural health monitoring is necessary to inspect damage of the 3D printed components. There is little research on the structural health monitoring methods of SCFRP, and the structural health monitoring methods have not been established. Electrical resistance change method (ERCM) is one of the structural health monitoring methods. This method will be applied to SCFRP. The application of ERCM has a problem that SCFRP exhibits insulation property when the fiber volume fraction is low. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to establish a structural health monitoring method using the electric property of insulating SCFRP and conductive SCFRP by self-sensing. Specimens were fabricated using two types of 3D printers and two types of SCFRP filaments. One is an insulating SCFRP, the other is a conductive SCFRP. Insulating SCFRP evaluated the capacitance, and conductive SCFRP evaluated the impedance. The relationship between strain and these electric property changes were investigated. Since the frequency of the alternating current and temperature affect the impedance change t , the experimental researches of these effects were carried out. The electric property change of insulating and conductive SCFRP was measured during the tensile test. The relationship between the strain of SCFRP and the change of these electric properties was clarified.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural health monitoring methods are useful for existing old mechanical components. Many structural health monitoring methods of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been reported [1-3]. Since the carbon fibers are a conductive material, it can be used as sensors when we measure electrical resistance change. The method does not require additional sensors, and the method is called the self-sensing method.

With the development of additive manufacturing technologies, it is possible to fabricate a complicated part by using 3D printer [4, 5]. Recently, short carbon fiber reinforced plastics (SCFRP) was adopted in 3D printer filaments. The mechanical properties are inferior to the continuous CFRP. We can make complicated components with small feature such as vibration metamaterial using the 3D printer [6]. The small feature brings difficulty for attaching a sensor. This indicates that the self-sensing function may be indispensable. There is a lot of research about self-sensing on short fiber composites which is using carbon nanotubes (CNT) [7, 8]. The electric resistance change is applied to CNT composite as a self-sensing method. Since the conductivity of CNT is superior to the conductivity of carbon fibers and aspect ratio of CNT is very high, The CNT composite has conductivity at small fiber volume fraction. The self-sensing method can be applied to short fiber composite such as a CNT composite using electrical resistance change. Only a few papers deal with the self-sensing in SCFRP [9].

Our research target is shown in Figure 1. The objective of our research is to develop a new structural health monitoring method using the electric property of insulating SCFRP and conductive

SCFRP with wireless system. The wireless strain measurement will be developed using radio frequency identification. In this paper, we used wire to measure strain wirelessly.

Figure 1: Outline of our research.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 3D printed short carbon fiber reinforced plastics

The electric property of SCFRP depends on the difference in fiber volume fraction. In order to investigate the electric property, the specimens were manufactured using two 3D printers and two SCFRP filaments. 3D printing path is shown in Figure 2. Since the fiber orientation of SCFRP aligned in a moving direction of a nozzle, the fiber orientation of the specimen was almost unidirectionally aligned. The SCFRP filaments used in the present paper were originally impregnated with short carbon fibers (SCF), and two types of fiber volume fraction were adopted. One is a commercially SCF/PA6 with low fiber fraction (insulating SCFRP) and the other is a SCF/PA6 with high fiber fraction of our own making (conductive SCFRP). The SCF/PA6 filament with high fiber volume fraction has made by filament extruder (Noztek Pro, Noztek Co.) using commercially SCF/PA6 pellets. The SCFRP after printing was shot by an X-ray computed tomography system, and the fiber volume fraction of each filament was checked. The lower one is 10% and the higher one is 50% respectively.

The dimensions of the insulating SCFRP (10% volume fraction) specimen were $120 \times 15 \times 1.0$ [mm]. The dimensions of the conductive SCFRP (50% volume fraction) specimen were $120 \times 15 \times 1.5$ [mm]. The difference in the thickness dimension comes from in the printing conditions.

Figure 2: 3D printing path

(a) Insulating SCFRP

(b) Conductive SCFRP

Figure 3: Specimen configuration and electric measurement method

In order to make electric property measurements, it is necessary to construct electric contact points (electrodes). The dimensions of the electrodes and the measurement method of each specimen are shown in Figure 3. Since an electric property measurement was impeded by insulator resin on the surface of the 3D printed specimen, it is necessary to remove the resin on the surface. The surface resin was removed using a laser processing machine (HAJIME, Oh-Laser Co.). The area is width 15 mm \times length 5 mm. Silver paste was applied to the surface after resin removal and kept at room temperature for 24 hours for curing. A lead wire was fixed on the cured silver paste using an adhesive, and the silver paste was applied again to make an electrode.

2.2 Alternating current measurement

LCR meter (IM3536, HIOKI E.E. Co.) was used to measure the electric property. The measurement was performed by the two-terminal method in insulating SCFRP because the electrical resistance is very large. As the measurement factor, the impedance and the impedance angle were measured, the capacitance was derived using Equation 1.

$$C_p = \sin \theta / 2 \pi f Z \quad (1)$$

Where θ is a phase angle, f is a measurement frequency and Z is an impedance.

In conductive SCFRP, the measurement was performed by the four-terminal method that eliminates the contact resistance because the electric resistance value of the conductive SCFRP is relatively small.

Alternating current of 1 kHz to 100 kHz was used in the measurement of insulating SCFRP. The measurement range was selected because there was small noise at the alternation current frequency. For the conductive SCFRP, 0.01 kHz to 100 kHz was adopted. For the conductive SCFRP, we could measure the impedance even in the low-frequency band without noise. Since the electric property also changes with the temperature, the temperature dependence between 0 degrees Celsius and 50 degrees Celsius was measured in each SCFRP.

2.3 Tensile test

In order to perform a tensile test, a strain gauge was attached to the back of the specimen front surface where the electrode was placed. Nylon resin tabs were attached to both ends.

Tensile tests were carried out by a universal testing machine (AG-100kN, Shimadzu Co.). The tensile test speed was 0.5 mm/min. In order to measure the electric property change, the measurement frequency was 10 kHz for both specimens and comparison was made up to a strain value of 0.3%. Three specimens were used to check the data scatter.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Frequency and temperature dependence

A typical example of the electric property of an insulating SCFRP measured to investigate the effects of frequency and temperature is shown in Figure 4(a). The horizontal axis shows frequency, and the vertical axis shows capacitance normalized with the capacitance at the room temperature. The collar of the symbols indicate the temperature. The capacitance decreases as the frequency increases at all temperatures. In addition, the capacitance increases as the temperature rises. The electric property of insulating SCFRP depends on frequency and temperature.

(a) Insulating SCFRP

(b) Conductive SCFRP

Figure 3: Frequency and temperature dependence

Typical examples of the electric property of a conductive SCFRP measured is shown in Figure 3(b). The horizontal axis shows frequency, and the vertical axis shows impedance normalized with the impedance at the room temperature. The plot colour indicates the difference of the temperature. The unstable behaviour in the measured impedance can be confirmed when the frequency is more than 10 kHz. The unstable behaviour is due to the influence of the reactance factor inside the measurement device such as lead wires. It was confirmed that the impedance is almost constant at all frequency below 10 kHz. However, the temperature change causes the impedance changes.

3.2 Tensile test

The relationship between strain and capacitance change of insulating SCFRP is shown in Figure 5(a). The vertical axis shows the applied strain, and the horizontal axis shows the capacitance change. It was confirmed that there is a linear relationship between strain and capacitance. This indicates that the self-sensing of the strain is possible by measuring the capacitance change.

The relationship between strain and impedance change of conductive SCFRP is shown in Figure 5(b). The vertical axis shows the strain, and the horizontal axis shows the impedance change. The relationship between the strain and the impedance change is nonlinear. This can be considered to be the effect of the tunnel current effect due to the displacement between fibers [10]. When we consider the nonlinearity of the relationship, the strain can be estimated from the impedance change.

(a) Insulating SCFRP

(b) Conductive SCFRP

Figure 4: Relationship between strain and electric property change

4 SUMMARIES

Self-sensing of strain was performed using the electric property in two types of SCFRP. Since the measurement of electric property adopted alternating current measurement, the influence investigation of frequency and temperature was conducted. The frequency and temperature dependence on the isolated SCFRP were clarified, and the frequency dependence on the conducting SCFRP is confirmed. The temperature dependence of the conductive SCFRP had to be clarified by conducting additional experiments.

The relationship between the strain and the electric property change is that the insulating SCFRP is linear and the conductive SCFRP is non-linear. Therefore, it was shown that self-sensing of strain using the capacitance change is possible, and it was shown that self-sensing of strain using the impedance change needs formulas considering the nonlinear effect s

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